

Research of Strength Criteria of Tridirectionally Woven Fiber Reinforced Composite Materials

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ABSTRACT

An improved method to establish the strength criteria of tridirectionally woven fiber reinforced composite materials is presented in this paper. This method is based on Tsai–Wu tensor theory and is improved by the least square method and introducing the idea of micromechanics. The Strength parameters in the strength criteria formula are determined integrally by the least square method to fit all the experimental data of the various stress states. The interacting strength parameters between the normal stress and shear stress in Tsai–Wu tensor theory are reserved according to the idea of micromechanics.

Finally, the allowable strength criteria formula is given upon the basis of statistics. It corresponds to the lower value of the strength above which at least 99% of experimental values should fall with a confidence of 90%.

Keywords: strength criteria, composite materials, 3DC / C

1. Introduction

Tridirectionally woven fiber reinforced composite(TWFRC), Such as the 3DC / C, is used in the thermostructures of the flight vehicle. To design the parts made of the TWFRC, the strength criteria is necessary. The study on the strength criteria of the 3DC / C was done by Prof.Gu^[1]. He gave the experimental data of the biaxial stress strength of the 3DC / C and presented the theory based on a quadratic function to fit the experimental data in each quadrant of a stress plane. However, there are several shortages in this theory. First, the strength criteria formula is very complicated. The values of the strength parameters in the formula are determined by the stress state. Hence, it consists of eight equations in fact. Secondly, The strength surface consists of eight surfaces, each of which is a part of ellipsoid. The sharp points or concavities are certainly formed in their interfaces. This is contrary to that the strength surface should be a convex surface.

Tsai–Wu Criteria ellipse shown in the reference [1] was determined by the value of the interacting

parameter F_{12} which was obtained by the experimental data of 1:1 biaxial extension stress state. If the value of F_{12} was obtained by the experimental data of 1:1 biaxial compressive stress state, the fitting of Tsai–Wu criteria ellipse with most of the experimental data would be fine. Hence, the reference [1] abandoned Tsai–Wu criteria is not reasonable.

An improved method to establish the strength criteria of the 3DC / C is presented in this paper. This method is based on Tsai–Wu tensor theory, and is improved by the least square method and introducing the idea of micromechanics.

2. Strength criteria

2.1. Tsai–Wu criteria improved by the least square method

Tsai–Wu tensor theory is a quadratic approach to the real strength surface. The number of the independent strength parameters in the criteria formula is very small. According to Tsai–Wu, each of the strength parameters in the strength criteria is determined by the experimental data of one or two stress states separately. Thus, it is difficult to make the strength ellipsoid better fitting to the experimental data of other stress states.

Tsai–Wu criteria improved by the least square method is presented in this paper. All of the experimental data which are relative to the various stress states are treated by the least square method integrally. Then, the parameters of the strength ellipsoid best fitting to all of the experimental data are determined. Obviously, each of the strength parameters in the strength criteria formula is no longer determined by the experimental data of one or two stress states, but by all of the experimental data of the various stress states integrally. The detail is as follows.

Generally, the 3DC / C has the same strength performance in the x direction and the y direction, then there are $F_1 = F_2$, $F_{11} = F_{22}$, $F_{13} = F_{23}$, and if $\sigma_4 = \sigma_5 = \sigma_6 = 0$ (when neglecting the shear stress), Tsai–Wu criteria formula is as follows

$$F_1(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2) + F_3\sigma_3 + F_{11}(\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2) + F_{33}\sigma_3^2 + 2F_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 + 2F_{13}(\sigma_1\sigma_3 + \sigma_2\sigma_3) = 1 \quad (1)$$

It is supposed that (X_i, Y_i, Z_i) is a group of the material principle direction strength values in some stress state, obtained in the i -th experiment. Substituting (X_i, Y_i, Z_i) for $(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3)$ of the equation 1 respectively, the error can be calculated as follows

$$R_i = 1 - [F_1(X_i + Y_i) + F_3Z_i + F_{11}(X_i^2 + Y_i^2) + F_{33}Z_i^2 + 2F_{12}X_iY_i + 2F_{13}(X_iZ_i + Y_iZ_i)] \quad (2)$$

From the n groups of the strength values obtained by experiments, the column matrix which consists of n error is as follows

$$\{R\}_{n \times 1} = \{1\}_{n \times 1} - [XYZ]_{n \times 6} \{F\}_{6 \times 1} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{where } [XYZ]_{n \times 6} = \begin{bmatrix} (X_1 + Y_1) & Z_1 & (X_1^2 + Y_1^2) & Z_1^2 & 2X_1Y_1 & 2(X_1Z_1 + Y_1Z_1) \\ (X_2 + Y_2) & Z_2 & (X_2^2 + Y_2^2) & Z_2^2 & 2X_2Y_2 & 2(X_2Z_2 + Y_2Z_2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ (X_n + Y_n) & Z_n & (X_n^2 + Y_n^2) & Z_n^2 & 2X_nY_n & 2(X_nZ_n + Y_nZ_n) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\{F\}_{6 \times 1} = [F_1 \ F_3 \ F_{11} \ F_{33} \ F_{12} \ F_{13}]^T$$

Calculating the sum of the error squares

$$\{R\}^T \{R\} = \{1\}^T \{1\} - 2\{F\}^T [XYZ]^T \{1\} + \{F\}^T [XYZ]^T [XYZ] \{F\} \quad (4)$$

According to the least square method, We have

$$\frac{\partial \{R\}^T \{R\}}{\partial \{F\}} = -2[XYZ]^T \{1\} + 2[XYZ]^T [XYZ] \{F\} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Form the equation 5, the parameters of the strength ellipsoid (i.e. the strength parameters) can be found

$$\{F\} = ([XYZ]^T [XYZ])^{-1} [XYZ]^T \{1\} \quad (6)$$

Substituting the experimental data of the 3DC / C given in the reference [1] into the equation 6, the following strength parameters in the criteria formula of the 3DC / C can be obtained

$$\left. \begin{aligned} F_1 &= 1.0132 \times 10^{-4} \text{MPa}^{-1} & F_3 &= -1.0649 \times 10^{-3} \text{MPa}^{-1} \\ F_{11} &= 3.4144 \times 10^{-5} \text{MPa}^{-2} & F_{33} &= 2.3681 \times 10^{-5} \text{MPa}^{-2} \\ F_{12} &= 3.1207 \times 10^{-6} \text{MPa}^{-2} & F_{13} &= 1.2779 \times 10^{-6} \text{MPa}^{-2} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

Figure 1 shows the ellipse of the strength criteria in the σ_1 - σ_2 plane, and Figure 2 shows that in the σ_1 - σ_3 plane. From the figures, it can be seen that the strength criteria established in this paper agrees with the experimental data fairly well.

Figure 1 The ellipse of the strength criteria in the σ_1 - σ_2 plane

Figure 2. The ellipse of the strength criteria in the σ_1 - σ_3 plane

2.2. Tsai–Wu criteria improved by the idea of micromechanics

There are interaction between the normal stress and shear stress in Tsai–Wu tensor theory, for example $F_{16}\sigma_1\sigma_6$, and so on. As the sign of the shear stress in the principle material coordinate system has no effect on the failure of materials, Tsai–Wu took $F_4 = F_5 = F_6 = 0$, and the interacting strength parameters between the normal stress and shear stress $F_{16} = \dots = 0$. Then, Tsai–Wu criteria which does not include the interaction between the normal stress and shear stress is presented. Tsai–Wu criteria is correct to the idea materials without any cracks in it. But, there are many of the micro-cracks on the interface of the matrix and the fiber in the 3DC / C, therefore from the idea of micromechanics the sign of the normal stress has some effect on the shear strength of the 3DC / C. The tension stress makes the interface crack large, and decreases the shear strength of the 3DC / C. The compression stress makes the interface crack closed, and increases the shear strength of the 3DC / C.

This point of view has been proved primarily by the experimental data of the tension–shear stress state, given in the reference [1]. Therefore, the present paper suggests introducing the interaction of the normal stress and shear stress in the strength criteria of the 3DC / C as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 & F_1(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2) + F_3\sigma_3 + F_{11}(\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2) + F_{33}\sigma_3^2 + 2F_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 \\
 & + 2F_{13}(\sigma_1\sigma_3 + \sigma_2\sigma_3) + F_{44}(\sigma_4^2 + \sigma_5^2) + F_{66}\sigma_6^2 \\
 & + 2F_{16}(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2)|\sigma_6| + 2F_{36}\sigma_3|\sigma_6| \\
 & + 2F_{14}(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2)(|\sigma_4| + |\sigma_5|) \\
 & + 2F_{34}\sigma_3(|\sigma_4| + |\sigma_5|) = 1
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

The strength parameters $F_1, F_3, F_{11}, F_{33}, F_{12}, F_{13}$ are given in the equation 7. $F_{44} = 1 / S_{YZ}^2$, $F_{66} = 1 / S_{XY}^2$, S_{YZ} and S_{XY} are the shear strength in the YZ plane and XY plane, respectively. In this way, We get $F_{44} = 4.4713 \times 10^{-4} \text{MPa}^{-2}$, $F_{66} = 7.9934 \times 10^{-4} \text{MPa}^{-2}$.

Referring to the experimental data of the tension–shear stress given in the reference [1], the following formula is recommended

$$\left. \begin{aligned} F_{16} &= 0.5\sqrt{F_{11}F_{66}} \\ F_{36} &= 0.5\sqrt{F_{33}F_{66}} \\ F_{14} &= 0.5\sqrt{F_{11}F_{44}} \\ F_{34} &= 0.5\sqrt{F_{33}F_{44}} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

Substituting the values of $F_{11}, F_{33}, F_{44}, F_{66}$ into the equation 9, We get $F_{16} = 8.260 \times 10^{-5} \text{MPa}^{-2}$, $F_{36} = 6.879 \times 10^{-5} \text{MPa}^{-2}$, $F_{14} = 7.432 \times 10^{-5} \text{MPa}^{-2}$, $F_{34} = 6.190 \times 10^{-5} \text{MPa}^{-2}$.

3. Allowable strength criteria

To design the parts made of the 3DC / C, the allowable strength criteria is necessary. Generally, the allowable strength criteria should correspond to the lower value of the strength above which at least 99% of the experimental values should fall with a confidence of 90%. Hence, the lower limit ellipsoid must be given by the statistical analysis.

Since the 3DC / C is very expensive, the number of the experimental data of same stress state is very small (for example 2or 3). An engineering method of the statistical analysis is presented in this paper.

First, transforming the sample of the like parent populations into the sample of one parent population, then the statistical analysis of all the experimental data of various stress states can be done.

It is supposed that the $(\sigma_{1i}, \sigma_{2i}, \sigma_{3i}, \sigma_{4i}, \sigma_{5i}, \sigma_{6i})$ are the i -th experimental data of the 3DC / C strength performance, substituting them into the left-hand part of the equation 8, the values of the left-hand part (dimensionless quantity) can be found as K_i .

Supposing that the K_i obeys the normal distribution, one can get the mean value \bar{K} and the standard deviation s of the sample, and then get the lower value K_{\min} above which at least 99% of the experimental data should be fall with a confidence of 90% as follows

$$K_{\min} = \bar{K} - L \cdot S \quad (10)$$

where L —the allowable limit factor.

The value of L depends on the sample size (i.e. the number of all the experimental data).

Using the experimental data of the reference [1], we obtain $K_{\min} = 0.61795$. Then the allowable strength criteria of the 3 DC / C can be found by substituting 0.61795 for 1 in the right-hand part of the equation 8. The ellipse of the allowable strength criteria in the σ_1 - σ_2 plane is shown in Figure 1 and that in the σ_1 - σ_3 plane is shown in the Figure 2.

4. Conclusion

(1) This paper presents an improved method to establish the strength criteria formula, in which all the strength parameters of the Tsai–Wu criteria are determined integrally by the least square method. It is much better than the general method in which each of the strength parameters is determined by the experimental data of one or two stress states.

The fitting of this method to the experimental data of the various stress states is improved obviously. It can eliminate the bad fitting of the strength criteria ellipsoid to the experimental data due to the wrong electing stress state of determining the interaction strength parameters, as reference [1].

(2) There are many micro–cracks inside the 3DC / C. According to the idea of micromechanics, the interaction between the normal stress and shear stress should be reserved. The interacting strength parameters should be determined by the tension–shear and the compressive–shear tests.

(3) The number of the experimental data of the same stress state is very small. Transforming the sample of the like parent populations into the sample of one parent population, the statistical analysis of all the experimental data of the various stress states can be done. In this way, the allowable strength criteria formula has been established and may be applied to designing the parts made of the 3 DC / C. It corresponds to the lower value of the strength performance above which at least 99% of the experimental data should fall with a confidence of 90%.

Reference

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